

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

PHONETIC AND FUNCTIONAL VARIABILITY OF STRESS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract

This article deals with phonetic structure and functional variability of stress in English. Like other languages, English has its own phonetic system and structure. The phonetic system of each language includes segmental and suprasegmental units. Segmental units are phonemes and combinations of phonemes in the language. Suprasegmental units do not exist separately. They exist together with segmental units. Suprasegment or suprasegmental units include stress, tones, length, intonation, etc. Both segment and suprasegmental units are very important in the learning process.

Keywords: segment, stress, syllable, dynamic, unstressed, polysyllabic.

Introduction. There are three aspects of the stress component in English. 1) the physical-acoustic nature of the stress, 2) the position of stress in two-syllable and polysyllabic words, 3) degree of stress.

R. Kingdon notes that, stress is the relative degree of force used by a speaker on the various syllables the speaker is uttering. It gives a certain basic prominence to the syllables, and hence to the words, on which it is used, and incidentally assists in avoiding monotony. There are two types of stress: Word or Lexical Stress and Sentence or syntactical Stress (Kingdon R, 1958).

Word stress is the relative degree of force used in pronouncing the different syllables of a word of more than one syllable. Monosyllables cannot be said to have word stress. Word stress in English is usually considered to occur in three degrees, which have been given various names by different authorities: 1. Primary, Strong, Main or Principal 2. Secondary, half Strong or Medium 3. Weak or Unstressed.

Sentence stress is the relative degree of force given to the different words in a sentence. Sentence stress may differ from word stress in either of two ways: Monosyllables may take sentence stress if they play an important enough part in the utterance, and words of more than one syllable may be unstressed if their function in the sentence is sufficiently unimportant.

According to D. Kristal and A.C. Gimson, word stress in English is a complex phenomenon that has strength, melody, quantitative and qualitative shades (Crystal, D, 1969). The dynamic and tonic features of word stress in English prevail over others (Gimson, A.G, 1975). M.A. Sokolova notes that each vowel in the words 'import' (noun) - 'im'port' (verb) words has the same tone due to its length, it is very difficult to distinguish them (Sokolova M.A, 1996). The placement of the change in the tonal level of the voice indicates the place of stress. It should be noted that the change of the tonal level of the voice does not affect the word stress.

H.A. Gleason and other American descriptors distinguish four degrees of word stress in English;

- 1) primary stress / ' /
- 2) secondary stress / ^ /

3) tertiary stress (emphasis) / ` /

4) weak stress / ~ /

The fourth type of accent is not marked in the examples. H.A. Gleason shows secondary accent and tertiary accent in the following examples.

bláck b`ird-bláck b`ird (Глисон Г. А., 1959). Word stress in English is traditionally characterized by its phonetic nature as force or dynamic stress. Dynamic stress means that the stressed syllable in the words is pronounced more tensely, more strongly than the others. At the same time, A. Gimson expresses the opinion that the variability of the tone of voice can be the most effective sign of prominence for the listener as a rule (Gimson, A.G, 1975). Recent experimental studies show that the prominence of the stressed syllable is expressed more by the pitch.

Length is also a strong factor in the prominence of a stressed syllable. Loudness and quality factor have little effect. P. Ladefoged shows that the stressed syllable in English is pronounced longer, stronger and with a higher tone than the unstressed one (Ladefoged P., 1982). From the above, it is clear that there is a diversity of opinions regarding the phonetic nature of stress in English.

One of the phonetic phenomena related to stress in English is the phenomenon of reduction. The dynamic stress used in the Germanic language family is most pronounced on vowels in unstressed syllables. The unstressed position of vowels has led to the emergence of a special phoneme in English. From the physiological-acoustic point of view, the neutral sound / ə / is the result of the weakening of vowels in the unstressed position. Unlike the neutral sound, the short / i / sound in English often acts as the unstressed equivalent of other vowels. But the neutral sound rather than / i / performs such a task. The neutral sound performs different functions in different situations. On the other hand, keeping the full form of a number of vowels in the unstressed state creates conditions for the neutral vowel to perform a functional task. For example;

exercise / 'eksəsaiz / - tapşırıq

exorcise / 'eksosaiz / - acı hissləri qovmaq.

In fact, these sounds act as the equivalent of different vowels. As it can be seen, the phonetic status of

some diphthongs / iə, uə / is related to stress in certain phonetic and morphological conditions. One of the phonetic phenomena related to stress in the language is phoneme alternation. Phonetic alternation is the substitution of one phoneme for another under certain phonetic conditions. For example; can / kæn / kən /, five pence / faif pens / . In phonological alternation, there are cases that are related to stress. For example; ; that / ðæt / - relative pronoun

that / ðæt / - demonstrative pronoun

Phonological alternation related to stress manifests itself in the following cases.

1. One vowel is replaced by another by changing the place of stress in the word. For example ; contrast / 'kontrəst / , / kən'træst / .

On the one hand, the change in the place of the stress leads to the replacement of one vowel by another, and on the other hand, to the differentiation of different parts of speech

2. Vowel substitution occurs in words with the same root as the stress changes. In this case. Words are distinguished both lexically and grammatically.

3. In words with the same root, both vowels and consonants replace each other by changing the place of the stress.

The unstressed state of vowels in English is observed first of all at the morphological level. Thus, stressed and unstressed derivatives arise from the same root.

One of the phenomena related to stress is the phenomenon of assimilation. An assimilated sound is usually unstressed. For example looked / lukt / .

In addition, the historical assimilation of many words in English is related to stress. This in itself is related to the recessive tendency of the English stress.

The random assimilation event that occurs in the speech process can be explained mainly by the fact that the syllables are in an unstressed state. Sometimes there are cases where assimilation can occur in a stressed syllable. In English, the place of stress in words, especially its degree, is influenced by a number of linguistic factors. In English two and three syllable words, the stress usually falls on the root. For example ; children, woman, aspirated, etc.

Stress differentiates verbs with the same lexical composition from a semantic point of view. For example; object, compound, etc. The semantic factor of stress ensures that prepositions are processed as adverbs from verb combinations and change the meaning of the verb. Each component of complex abbreviations carries stress depending on its semantic point of view. One of the factors that determine the place of stress in polysyllabic words in English is the syllabic factor. Since syllabic syllable and rhythmic factors are closely related to each other, they act as determinants of each other. Depending on the degree of meaning and the number of syllables, the accent-rhythmic structure of the word also changes, and in this case the emphasis is divided into two parts, primary and secondary. So, changing the syllabic structure of a word affects its accent-rhythmic structure.

In English, the processing of secondary stress in polysyllabic words is primarily determined by the

rhythmic factor of stress. Each language is characterized by its own speech forms and accent-rhythmic structures. The syllabic structure of words consisted of one, two and rarely three syllables. Therefore, in words with few syllables, the stress fell on the root syllable, creating a rhythmic structure alternating with unstressed syllables. This rhythmic trend in the word also affected the speech process and had a strong influence on the emergence of a certain rhythmic norm in speech.

One of the tendencies accompanying English words is the retentive tendency. This tendency means keeping the stress on the root syllable in words from the same root. For example ; 'person', 'personal', 'personally', 'personality' etc.

It should also be kept in mind that in many borrowing words, the stress has been subject to a prototypic tendency rather than a recessive tendency, keeping its place. For example ; vibrate, sonorous, mountaineer, etc.

In English, the rhythmic factor is so strong that words with two strong stresses may lose one of the stresses within a sentence, or the main meaning word may be unstressed. For example ; She 'went home – 'Jerry went 'home. Due to the influence of the rhythmic factor, the place of the so-called stress can change. For example ; diplo'matic, a 'diplomatic 'mission, 'Piccadily 'Circus

Thus, the following conclusion can be drawn from the above.

The place of stress in English words is determined by the presence of a number of factors and tendencies, and on this basis, words are formed as a linguistic unit.

One of the main factors determining the place of stress in English is the semantic factor.

a) The semantic factor implies that the stress falls on the root syllable of the word and the morpheme that carries the main meaning load. For example, 'reading, 'personal, be'fore, celeb'rate, etc.

b) As a result of the strong tendency of the semantic factor, compound nouns in English are mainly characterized by one, compound adjectives by two word combinations, and phraseological combinations by two or more stresses. For example ; 'dark- 'eyed, 'out of 'sight, etc.

It is due to the influence of the semantic factor that the second component of compound nouns can carry stress according to the degree of meaning load. For example, 'tea' set, 'arm-'chair, 'ice -'cream, etc.

c) According to the requirement of the semantic factor, each component of complex abbreviation words receives stress. For example, 'U'S'B'S, 'U'S'A, etc.

One of the factors determining the place of stress in English is the grammatical factor.

One of the factors determining the place and degree of stress in polysyllabic words is the rhythmic factor.

The rhythmic factor implies the substitution of stressed and unstressed syllables in two and polysyllabic words, or the pronunciation of stressed syllables at the same time. In English, in addition to the above factors, there are a number of tendencies that determine the place of stress.

As it can be seen, the place and degree of word stress in English is determined by various factors and trends. However, the semantic and rhythmic factors play a decisive role in them.

In English, words consisting of two or more syllables and pronounced separately are characterized by a specific degree of stress. In words, one or more syllables are distinguished from other syllables by their prosodic features. When we pronounce the words we feel such a difference. Stressed syllables are pronounced stronger, louder, clearer, in a higher tone than unstressed syllables. Such stress is called dynamic stress. Stress in English is dynamic. In English, syllables in words differ from each other in terms of the degree of stress: strong stress or main, relatively weak, very weak or unstressed. For example ; 'Oxford, 'congress, con'clusion, 'city.

In English, according to its place stress is mostly free. Thus, the stress in the words can be in different positions, at the beginning, in the middle and at the end of the word.

1. In English words consisting of two or three syllables, the stress falls on the root syllable - the beginning of the word. For example ; 'childhood, 'mother, 'something, etc.

2. In words with a weak first syllable, the stress falls on the second syllable. For example ; again, for-give, etc.

3. In a group of two-syllable words, the stress falls on the second syllable. For example ; res'pect, de'void, ma'chine, &c.

4. In polysyllabic words ending with suffixes -ise, -ize, -fy, -ate, the stress falls on the third syllable of the word, and on the fourth syllable in four-syllable verbs. For example ; recog'nize, terrify, appreciate, etc.

5. The accent falls on the second syllable from the end of the words ending with the suffixes -ion, -sion, -ion, -ian, -ent, -al, -tial, -ual, -ous, -ar. For example ; o'pinion, di'vision, lo'cation, etc.

6. In four-syllabic words ending with the suffixes -ity, -ety, logy, -logist, -graphy, -grapher, -cracy, the stress falls on the third syllable from the end. For example ;

bi'ologist, geo'o'graphy, pho'nology, etc.

7. In words ending in -er, -or, -ly, -cy, -ness, -full, -less, -ing, -ty, -hood and other suffixes, the stress is mainly on the root syllable. For example; 'actor, 'teacher, 'beautiful, 'manhood, 'property və s.

II. In English, words with four or more syllables are pronounced with two stresses, as a rule, according to the requirement of the rhythmic factor.

In polysyllabic words ending with the suffixes -tion, -ian, -ity, the stress falls on the syllable before the suffix, and the secondary stress falls on the first syllable from the beginning. For example ; compo'sition, demonstration, etc.

In English, depending on the number of syllables, the demands of rhythmic and semantic factors, polysyllabic words can have two secondary, one strong stress.

III. There is a group of words in the English language that are characterized, in terms of degree, by two main stresses. .

1. Negative prefixes: -un, -non, -in, -il, -ir.

For example ; unnamed, irresponsible.

2. -ex- in the sense of the past. For example ; 'ex' minister.

3. - re- means again, repeatedly. For example ; 're'cognize.

4. - mis- in the sense of wrong, not correct. For example ; 'mis'print.

5. -pre- in advance, earlier. 'pre'paid.

6. -out- much. outgo, 'out'do .

7. -over- too much. 'over'loud.

8. -under- assistant, subordinate person. For example ; 'under' go.

9. - anti- anti- 'anti'national.

10. -sub- deputy, assistant. - 'sub' editor.

11. -inter- between, within - 'inter'change.

12. half- half- 'half'baked.

13. Vice-assistant-'vice-'president.

14. Arch- chief, great.- 'arch'duke.

15. ultra- ultra- 'ultra'asionable.

IV. In English, numbers with the suffix -teen have two strong stresses. For example; 'nine'teen.

2. Compound adjectives, as a rule, have two strong stresses. For example ; 'blue-'eyed.

3. Since the first component of compound nouns has more semantic load, the stress falls on the first component of the word. For example ; 'music hall.

a) Depending on the value of the semantic load, both components of a number of compound nouns carries stress. For example ; 'armc'hair

b) In some compound nouns, the stress falls on the second component. For example, man'kind .

c) Compound verbs consisting of verbs and prepositions have two accents. 'Bring 'up, 'make 'up.

V. Due to the influence of the rhythmic tendency in English, words and phrases that have two stresses lose one of their stresses within the sentence. This is called rhythmic variation of word stress. For example: 'engineer- a' good engineer

VI. In English, compound abbreviations are characterized by equal stress. For example ; G.P.O.- General Post Office. Eleven accent and more than a hundred syllabic-rhythmic structures of words related to stress are distinguished in English. The accent type and the syllabic-rhythmic structure of the words interact with each other, and the morphological structure of the words in the language is determined by the syllable composition and the semantic load of the roots and suffixes.

The influence of the rhythmic factor shows its expression in the fact that, in accordance with the strong rhythmic tendency of English word stress, there is a tendency to develop additional stress in complex words with three or more syllables.

Although complex words and word combinations are more diverse in terms of lexical content and grammatical form, they are more stable in terms of accent structure.

Conclusion. the analysis of the materials of the English language helps us to come to the following conclusions: Linguistic sources indicate that word stress performs distinctive, culminating, delimitative or demarcating functions, and it is noted that with the help of stress, it is possible to determine how many words

there are in the speech act, including how many peaks and where the morphological border is. In English, the stressed word performs constitutive, distinctive, recognitive function. Equal stress in English is mainly manifested by the influence of the semantic factor.

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STYLISTIC TECHNIQUES OF REPRESENTING HUMOUR IN VIRTUAL GAMING DISCOURSE (ON THE MATERIAL OF THE SERIES SOUTH PARK GAMES)

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СТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ СПОСОБЫ РЕПРЕЗЕНТАЦИИ ЮМОРА В ВИРТУАЛЬНО-ИГРОВОМ ДИСКУРСЕ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ СЕРИИ ИГР «SOUTH PARK»)

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Abstract

The article presents the linguistic characteristics of virtual gaming discourse on the material of the games South Park: The Stick of Truth and South Park: The Fractured But Whole, including a description of its characteristic features, the definition of the humorous component of the games, as well as a stylistic analysis of their texts.

Аннотация

В данной статье представлена лингвистическая характеристика виртуально-игрового дискурса на материале серии игр «South Park»: «South Park: The Stick of Truth» и «South Park: The Fractured But Whole», включающая в себя описание его характерных особенностей, определение юмористического компонента игр, а также стилистический анализ их текстов.

Keywords: analysis, discourse, game, comic effect, user, stylistic device, expressive mean, emotivity, humor.

Ключевые слова: анализ, дискурс, игра, комический эффект, пользователь, стилистическое средство, изобразительно-выразительное средство, эмотивность, юмор.

Как известно, эмоции и чувства всегда мотивировали человека к познавательной деятельности, выступая одними из самых важных элементов его когнитивной системы. Наука, изучающая субъективные компоненты восприятия единиц языка, эмотиология, или же лингвистика эмоций, на сегодняшний момент является одной из передовых сфер языкознания, поскольку, ввиду недавнего смещения направления научного знания в сторону антропоцентризма, интерес учёных к установлению взаимосвязи эмоционального и рационального в познании человеком действительности возрастает.

За последние десятилетия дискурс видеоигр потерпел большие изменения, значительно увеличив своё поле. Можно сказать, что сегодня практически каждая компьютерная игра содержит в себе тексты, связанные не только с механикой игрового процесса, но и с художественным повествованием.

Многие разработчики теперь обращаются к введению в их продукт сюжета, который в свою очередь выражается с помощью комплексных художественных текстов, передающихся через нарратив, диалоги и прочие формы. Передача эмоций и чувств является одной из самых главных функций подобных текстов, поскольку их основу составляет система образов и идей, с помощью которых разработчик передаёт своё отношение к предмету речи. И эмоции, выражающие эти образы и идеи, в таком случае выступают посредниками отражения мира в языке. Немало важно сказать, что игровые художественные тексты имеют значительные отличительные особенности, если сравнивать их, например, с литературной прозой или текстами кино-дискурса, так как в видеоиграх текст зачастую подкрепляется визуальным, невербальным, повествованием, а реплики персонажей и сюжетный ход определяются